

HIGH STRAIN FRACTURE AND DEFORMATION CHARACTERISTICS OF THERMOSET MATRICES AND THEIR ROLE IN MATRIX DOMINATED FAILURE IN OFF-AXIS LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

It has been shown that the matrix in a transverse unidirectional graphite/epoxy laminate exhibits greater strength than the equivalent bulk resin. The extent of size-effect contributions to this improvement has been investigated and this suggests a degree of plasticity in the micro-mechanics of composite failure. Deformation and fracture processes of two epoxy thermosets have been studied in thin film form. Observations after exposure to high strain levels indicate that the bulk thermosets are capable of displaying plasticity in tension. Microcracks are seen with highly deformed bridging material. It is suggested that such processes are relevant to off-axis failure in the composite when there are no macroscopic flaws present.

INTRODUCTION

A lengthy and costly procedure of testing and verification is generally imperative before new materials can be approved for use in critical structures such as aerospace applications. In the case of fibre reinforced composites a rigorous micromechanical analysis could predict the thermoelastic and strength properties of the material from the basic properties of its constituents; fibre, matrix and the interface. One area of particular interest for the application of micro-mechanics analyses is the prediction of matrix dominated failures of laminae, since multiple matrix cracking in off-axis plies in laminates reduces the effective properties of the laminate and may lead to other types of damage (e.g. delamination) and render a component unfit for service.

The present work is part of a much wider programme of investigation that aims to provide accurate and comprehensive constituent characterisation for numerical and analytical predictive analysis. Here we intend to show that even some of the most brittle epoxy thermosets can display distinct levels of tensile plastic deformation in experiments that aim to imitate to some extent the size-effect and constraint that apply to the matrix in a transversely loaded lamina.

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL

Materials: The primary matrix under investigation is a proprietary unmodified epoxy (Ciba Composites Ltd F922) based on tetraglycidyl diamino diphenyl methane (TGDDM) cured

with diamino diphenyl sulphone (DDS) at 175°C for two hours to give a relatively brittle system with a T_g of over 200°C. Another thermoset has been used for comparative studies, namely Shell Epikote 828 cured with nadic methyl anhydride (NMA) and K61B accelerator (tris,2-ethylhexoate). This system is cured at 100°C for three hours followed by a post cure at 150°C for three hours.

Reference will be made to results from uniaxial graphite fibre laminates [1] which were made from Tenax HTA 513X f12000 fibre with the standard oxidative surface treatment (100%) and with no surface treatment (0%).

Bulk resin tensile, compressive and flexural tests: Plaques of various thicknesses in the range of 1 to 3 mm were cast between glass plates. Shims were used to control the thickness while silicone rubber tubes were used as seals for the mould. The plaques were then machined to size for the tensile and flexural tests [2,3]. Further cylindrical specimens were cast in glass tubes and after further turning operations these were used for compression tests [2].

In order to explore further the tensile strength behaviour a novel sandwich test was devised. This consisted of a coupon (150 x 20 mm) with a central core cut from a cured resin plaque, sandwiched between two 0.5 mm thick plies of uniaxial glass-reinforced epoxy resin. The sandwich laminate was prepared by grinding a sheet of cured F922 resin to the required thickness (0.6 to 2.4 mm) and then overwinding with glass fibre roving. The glass was then impregnated with resin, consolidated and cured under flat glass plates in an oven. The tougher 828/NMA/K61B resin mix was used for the outer layer so that coupons could be extended in tension to over 2.5 % strain. During the loading ramp a series of clearly visible transverse cracks developed within the central resin layer which were captured by strain synchronised photography. The cracks are analogous to transverse cracking in a [0,90,0] composite coupon. The data were analyzed using a Weibull model and an approach in line with Peters et al [4], to obtain statistical strength distributions for the resin. The same sandwich configuration was also adapted to measure the cracking characteristics of unidirectional transverse CFRP laminates thereby making GFRP/CFRP hybrid cross-pplies. The experimental and analytical techniques are described more fully elsewhere [1,2].

Thin film tensile tests: Thin films of degassed epoxy resin were coated on to pre-heated metal substrates. In order to obtain a uniform thickness the substrates were placed between glass plates under nominal pressure during the cure cycle in the oven. Having carefully removed the excess resin overflows, the dumb-bell substrates were loaded at a strain rate of 1%/min. Simultaneous strain measurements were made using a 50 mm gauge-length extensometer.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Role of Flaws: The epoxy system under investigation has been characterised in bulk and in UD carbon laminae and the basic mechanical properties are given in Table 1. The matrix dominated properties of the composite such as intra-laminar strength and toughness are superior to those of the bulk.

Fractographic examination of transverse fracture surfaces suggests that early/low strength failures in a typical length of coupon subject to multiple failure are due to the occurrence of foreign-body flaws or trapped voids, etc. However, higher strength fractures tend to be free of such obvious features and the source of failure could not be identified.

It has been shown that flaws/inclusions of the range 10 μm to 200 μm diameter are commonly present in the uncured resin [2]. Although an attempt at filtering resulted in

a 20% increase in mean strength of the bulk resin, its success was limited due to the very low toughness (Table 1) of the resin. This is because the system is prone to failure at minuscule surface and internal inconsistencies and flaws of only a few microns in diameter (e.g. a 20 μm diameter embedded penny-shaped flaw fails at 120 MPa applied tensile stress). The composite's intra-laminar toughness however is some 300 % greater and is thus more tolerant of existing flaws (e.g. a 110 μm diameter embedded penny-shaped flaw is required to fail at 120 MPa applied stress).

Furthermore, fractographic examinations have shown that when the interfacial strength of the fibre and matrix is increased by means of a standard oxidative surface treatment, the locus of failure is seen to lie in the matrix and the failure process can be classed as cohesive. The relevance of this point is in discounting the role of interfacial failure or fibre debonds as a means of subcritical damage formation when interfacial bond strength is controlled.

Strength Distributions and Weibull Analyses: Figure 1 can be regarded as a measure of size-effect of the TGDDM/DDS resin. Here a set of data points for the mean failure strain of various thicknesses of bulk F922 sandwich laminates are shown. The data have been plotted as a weak-link-scaling graph. Mean and standard deviation of some conventional bulk resin tensile coupons are also included in the graph. The inverse of the slope of the fitted straight line indicates the Weibull exponent for the whole data set to be about 7.0 This figure also represents the average Weibull modulus value of the individual Weibull strength distribution plots [1,2]. The size-effect trends which have also been verified by other results in the literature [5] indicate that the matrix in the composite in a typical inter-fibre region is, by virtue of its small volume, probabilistically capable of sustaining failure strains far in excess of the bulk and greater than 4 % strain. The estimated strength is based on certain assumptions and should not be regarded as absolute. It is also important to point out that Weibull statistics only allows for extrapolation of strength for an equal probability of failure which means that when considering the strength of the composite all the available resin within the sample gauge-length has to be considered. On that basis the overall strength of the resin in the composite will be significantly less than the equivalent strength of a single inter-fibre layer of resin.

Figure 2 is a plot of cumulative probability of failure against failure strain (mechanical and thermal) for the transverse tensile strength of treated (100%) and untreated (0%) HTA fibre in F922, as well as bulk F922 resin strength. The data were obtained from the sandwich technique. For the present purposes it is sufficient to state that the technique assumes that the gauge length of the core is divided by a chosen segment length (2.4 mm in the case here) such that each segment fails only once. This approach allows each failure to be assigned to a fixed volume of material and therefore based on the expected number of cracks the probability of failure may be derived. Since in some of the cases the total number of observed events exceeded the expected number by a few percent, the probability axis has been extended to beyond 1 to include all the experimental data.

Close examination of figure 2 shows that the composite matrix is displaying a greater strength than the resin in bulk form. At first sight the bulk resin appears to be failing at a significantly higher strain than the composite incorporating the treated fibre. However, since the transverse modulus of the fibre is nearly four times the resin modulus a strain magnification factor will exist in the matrix. The model of Kies [6] can be used to calculate the strain magnification which is of the order of 3.0 in a 60% volume fraction square array composite. This means that for example at the mean value of the strain distribution, matrix in the composite is failing at approximately 4.0 % strain.

Experimental Observations of Damage at High Strain: In order to characterise the tensile deformation and fracture of low toughness thermosets at high strain (which is pertinent

to matrix in a composite) it is necessary to utilise small test samples, since large gauge volumes are much more likely to have pre-existing critical flaws within them that lead to premature brittle failure. It is advantageous to attach the test piece to a material of higher modulus so as to promote a constraint effect in the test-piece. This is analogous to the constraint experienced by thin transverse plies in a cross-ply laminate [7]. It is also advantageous to build in some form of damage containment such that post mortem examination of the brittle and often explosive failure could be carried out. Therefore, thin films of the epoxy were coated onto aluminium alloy substrates and were then loaded in tension. Figure 3 is an SEM photomicrograph of a thin film of F922 epoxy on aluminum substrate which has been loaded to about 8 % tensile strain. The film has suffered multiple failure and appears to have delaminated locally from the substrate which is visible in the background. It can be noted that in some cases fibrils of the polymer are bridging the microcrack and show visibly high levels of local plastic deformation.

Figure 4 is a transmitted light photomicrograph that shows the tensile face of a thin plaque of the 828/NMA/K61B bulk epoxy which has been deformed in three point bending to the onset of yield. The long features seen here densify with increasing strain and are aligned perpendicular to the load axis. They also appear to have depth profiles as was evident by focusing into them. Figure 5 is an SEM photomicrograph of a 828/NMA/K61B three point bend specimen which has failed just beyond its yield point in tension. Cavitational microcracking stabilised and bridged by fibrils of drawn polymer is clearly visible. These features are aligned at 90° to the uniaxial stress field suggesting initiation and propagation to be controlled by the highest dilational stress tensor. It is noteworthy that all the features reported here have occurred at or beyond the onset of deviation from the elastic/anelastic regions of the materials in tension and are thus likely to be intrinsic modes of material deformation.

The mean value of transverse flexural strength (TFS) of the F922/HTA 5131 laminate is given in Table 1 as 111 MPa. However, it became apparent subsequently that this strength value can be increased by about 20 % after removing the resin-rich peel ply texture and subsequently polishing the tensile face of the TFS specimen. This effect, which has been reported by Curtis et al. [8], is due to removal of the surface inconsistencies which act as stress raisers and limit strength. However, the interesting point here is that the increased strength has facilitated the observation of fracture artifacts on the fracture surface of the TFS specimens. Figure 6 shows the highest stressed area of the TFS fracture surface (i.e along the edge on the original tensile face) where the fracture morphology is indicative of highly deformed polymer with evidence of a collapsed fibrillar structure. No other causes of failure (e.g. flaws or inclusions) could be identified on the most highly stressed areas and the remainder of the surface has no outstanding features. It is interesting to note that the theoretical surface defect size at the failure stress of 135 MPa is of the order of 30 μm which is in agreement with the dimensions of the indicated area.

The discussions so far have indicated that highly cross-linked epoxies are capable of undergoing high levels of local plastic deformation in tension provided that the conditions dictated by size-effect and dilational stress tensor are met. These conditions appear to be satisfied for the matrix in a transversely loaded composite and in particular for the thin inter-fibre regions. Nedele and Wisnom [9] have carried out finite element analyses which show that a condition of hydrostatic tension can exist around fibres in a transversely loaded graphite-epoxy lamina. It is proposed that subcritical microcracks can evolve in a transversely loaded composite which eventually extend and/or interact to form critical flaws. This mechanism is proposed to aid the construction of a sound micromechanical model for a fundamental description of transverse cracking in a thermoset polymer composite.

CONCLUSIONS

Comparison of the bulk strength of a standard prepregging epoxy resin with that of the matrix in transversely loaded UD laminates have shown that the in-situ composite matrix is stronger than the bulk. This phenomenon cannot be explained solely in terms of size-effect. It has been shown that the same thermosetting resin is capable of large levels of local plastic deformation under tensile loading. Based on the experimental evidence it is proposed that epoxy resins can develop intrinsically driven cavitation microcracking. The requirements for this dilational mechanism of deformation obviate their occurrence in conventional bulk samples where other brittle fracture processes take precedence. However, the conditions can be satisfied for a matrix in the inter-fibre regions within a composite.

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Table 1:
Mechanical properties of the TGDDM/DDS bulk epoxy resin and the associated composite.

	GPa	MPa	%	MPa	MN m ^{-3/2}
properties : bulk epoxy resin					
	Young's modulus	tensile strength	tensile failure strain	compressive yield	fracture toughness
standard Fiberdux 922	3.89 ± 0.04	50.0 ± 7.5	1.50 ± 0.22	174 ± 1.5	0.43 ± 0.02
transverse properties : Tenax HTA/F922 UD laminates with different surface treatments					
	Young's modulus	transverse tensile strength	mean failure strain	flexural transverse strength	intralaminar fracture toughness
untreated 0%	9.08	39 ± 3.4	0.45	54 ± 4.6	1.07
treated 100%	9.95	64 ± 4.7	0.71	111 ± 17	1.51

Figure 1:

Weibull weak link scaling plot based on the data from the sandwich tests on the bulk F922 epoxy resin. Mean and standard deviation data from conventional tensile tests are also included.

Figure 2: Cumulative distribution curves for the strain-to-failure of F922 bulk resin [R], and transverse laminates made with untreated [0%] and standard surface treated [100%] HTA 513X carbon fibres in F922 resin.

Figure 3: SEM photomicrograph of a thin film TGDDM/DDS resin (F922) coated on an aluminium substrate loaded in tension to achieve multiple failure in the thin film.

Figure 4: Transmitted light photomicrograph of a thin three point bend specimen of Epikote 828/NMA/K61B epoxy resin showing features that have grown perpendicular to the principal tensile load direction. These features densify and grow with further strain. Size bar 10 μm .

Figure 5: SEM photomicrograph of a bulk three point bend specimen of Epikote 828/NMA/K61B epoxy resin which has been loaded to beyond a clear yield point in tension. The tensile face of the specimen is shown where microcavitation cracking has grown perpendicular to the principal tensile load direction.

Figure 6: SEM photomicrograph of a high strength transverse flexure fracture surface showing the edge of a the tensile face where evidence of local plasticity in the form of collapsed fibrils highlight the point of crack initiation.